

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: 60 mm TPS Sensor Recommended for Testing Large Heterogeneous Concrete Samples

The following Application Highlight addresses the testing of concrete using the C-Therm Trident™. This document highlights the benefits of testing heterogeneous samples with the 60mm TPS.

Concrete is a composite material produced by mixing cement and water with aggregates, and it is the most widely used building material globally. Many different concretes are available based on the ratio and types of aggregates used. These variables influence the end product's mechanical strength and thermal resistance, which are tailored to the specific engineering application requirements. As a thermal performance metric, thermal conductivity (k) is a highly investigated property of interest. When measuring the thermal conductivity of concrete, there are a few special considerations to be aware of.

Figure 1 - Trident with FLEX TPS pictured next to concrete samples.

Concrete and other porous media are often hygroscopic, meaning that they will react or absorb water. Some analysis methods require the application of a coating or contact agent between the sample and the sensor for testing. These methods are typically not an effective way to test these sample types due to compatibility issues. This is one of the reasons why the FLEX Transient Plane Source (TPS) method is an ideal candidate for the testing of concrete, as the sensor is put in direct contact with the sample without any treatments or contact agent requirements. Due to the flexible nature of the sensor, it is also ideal for dealing with these rougher sample types that may be potentially damaging to other sensor form factors and more cumbersome from a sample machining perspective.

Thermal conductivity is a measure of a material's ability to transfer heat. In a homogenous medium, irrelevant to the assessed volume, thermal conductivity results will be highly consistent assuming a proper method is employed. For a material such as concrete, which is highly heterogeneous, the effective thermal conductivity can vary depending on the assessed volume of the material. Often times a larger evaluated volume is desirable to obtain a more representative understanding of performance.

Figure 2 – Depiction of different volumes of material assessed based on TPS sensor size.

The following data highlights the measurement of a *quick-crete* concrete sample using the 60 mm TPS sensor sizes under ambient RT conditions. Testing was performed at 3 different locations across the material to assess consistency. All testing was performed following best practices as outlined in ISO 22007-2 for bulk material characterization.

Figure 3 - Thermal conductivity results on quick-crete.

As shown in the results above, the thermal conductivity of the quick-crete sample varied slightly based on the location of measurement. An average value of 2.20 W/mK was obtained with an RSD of 5.5%. Overall this compares well with the expected range of concrete (1.6-3.2 W/mK¹), which is highly specific to the composition, conditions of measurement, and method of analysis.

To learn more about C-Therm’s Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com

¹ J. Environ. Treat. Tech. 2020, Volume 8, Issue 3, Pages: 908-914